

Annex 5. Photographic annex exemplifying different points according to their risk score (Table 1); the actions proposed in each case and an estimation of the materials, work, and cost (Table 2) of the intervention, in €. See Martínez-Guijosa et al. 2021.

Risk 1

Description

Proposed measures

Feeder, enclosed and fully protected against wildlife

Habitual hygiene and maintenance

Water trough, enclosed and fully protected against wildlife

Habitual hygiene and maintenance

Water reservoir. 150 x 70 meters. Fenced with livestock fence. Inaccessible to cattle.

Periodic maintenance of the fence to ensure proper operation

Risk 2

Description

Large water trough with concrete base.
Clean interior.
0.8 meter high.
No signs of wildlife

Proposed measures

Regular hygiene and maintenance

Plot where the hay is stored. Perimeter livestock fence with barbed wire 1.5 meter high. No signs of wildlife

Periodic review of the fence to ensure proper operation and to detect the possible entry of wildlife

Temporary stream. Rain runoff. It enters and leaves the farm, runs through two plots along 900 meters. No signs of wildlife.

Measure 1

Install an electric shepherd to avoid access to the stream when livestock enter the affected plots and the stream is not completely dry

Measure 2

Allow access to affected plots only when the stream is completely dry or flowing abundantly and does not form pools or ponds

Risk 3

Description	Proposed measures
Metallic feeder with roof, on a fenced plot with a 1.5 meter-high cattle fence with boar pass. No evidence of use by wildlife	Repair the fence. Periodic review of the fence to ensure proper operation and to detect the possible entry of wildlife
Metallic water trough 1 meter high. Good hygiene. Without cement base. Wild boar scratching in the vicinity. No evidence of use by wildlife	Habitual hygiene and maintenance. Install cement base
Permanent large pond. 140 x 30 meters. Deer droppings in the immediate vicinity. Remains of an old cattle fence	Repair the fence or install a new one so that the cattle cannot access the banks of the pond. Installation of a high water trough in the vicinity

Risk 4

Description	Proposed measures
Permanent small pond. 17 x 17 meters. Its size is drastically reduced in summer. Some signs of wildlife	Install a livestock fence so that the cattle cannot access the banks of the pond. Installation of a high water trough in the vicinity
Large stream that maintains water all year round. Its flow is drastically reduced in summer, forming pools and backwaters. It affects a plot on the farm, 1 kilometer long. Some signs of wildlife	Measure 1 Divide the affected plot in half, fencing the stream in the west. On the new plot generated to the east, only graze while the stream water runs, avoiding grazing when ponding Measure 2 Prevent cattle from entering the affected plot
Low-rise prefabricated water trough designed for pigs. 0.25 meters high. Some signs of wildlife	Duplicate (install new) water troughs, providing cattle with one of greater capacity and height, and (i) close the water supply to the pig waterer when it is not going to be used or (ii) install a livestock fence or a lid so that cattle cannot use it

Risk 5

Description	Proposed measures
Small shallow pond that dries in late summer. 10 x 5 meters. Signs of wild boar and badger.	<p>Measure 1 Prevent cattle from gaining access to the affected plot while the pond contains water</p> <p>Measure 2 Peripheral livestock fence. Leave it for the use of wildlife and water cattle at nearby water troughs</p>
Flooded and shady spring. 3 x 3 meters. With a large muddy area, which extends several meters to one side. Remains of an old cattle fence. Signs of wild boar	<p>Measure 1 If possible, eliminate flooded area by means of burial</p> <p>Measure 2 Install a livestock fence so that the cattle cannot gain access. Condition the spring in order to channel the water and take it to a fenced pond or a trough with the appropriate characteristics</p>
Water trough at ground level with flooded area. Signs of wild boar and deer	<p>Eliminate. If pigs are going to enter during acorn mast, replace with a pig water trough, and (i) close the water supply to the pig waterer when it is not going to be used or (ii) install a livestock fence or a lid so that cattle cannot use it</p>

Table 1. Estimated costs of interventions (unit price, in €)

Item	Unit price
Livestock fence	6€ linear meter/ 8€ linear meter and assembly
Game fence	10€ linear meter/ 12€ linear meter and assembly
Electric fence	Power unit: 160€ Cable: 14€/250m Steak: 3€ (2€ fibreglass, 4€ plastic)
Water trough (cattle)	170€/ 190€ with assembly and basement
Water trough (pig)	150€ with assembly
Backhoe	200€/day
Selective bump gates	Fence 14€ linear meter and assembly Gate 300€
Pipe and fittings	Pipe 55€ /100 m Fitting 5€
10,000 L tank	3000€
Porcine ELISA test	3€ /animal
Feeder	275€ with assembly
Worker	14€/hour
Bag of cement	3.45€/ 35 Kg

Table 2. Key employed to score the interaction risk between wildlife and extensive livestock at aggregation points. The risk is scored in a scale from 0 (without risk) to 5 (highest risk).

Site typology and characteristics	Risk Score (0–5)
Not accessible to livestock	0
Not accessible to wildlife	1
Waterer/feeder	
Low waterer/feeder¹ (≤ 90 cm height)	3
High waterer/feeder² (>90 cm height)	2
Water body^{3,4}	
Small waterhole (≤25 m Ø), spring or waterlogged river/stream	4
Large waterhole (>25 m Ø) or flowing river/stream	3
Food storage	
Closed building	0
Open air/accessible to wildlife	2
<u>Score modifiers</u>	
Signs of wildlife⁵	+2
Waterer with mud presence in its base⁶	+1
Water point totally dry in summer	-1
Water point with rocky or stony shore (no mud)	-1

¹ Not wild boar-proof.

² Wild boar-proof.

³ In the case of reservoirs, the nature of the banks will be considered to equate it to the waterhole that represents it

⁴ In a river or stream, the point/points that represent the greatest risk along its banks will be considered and scored as independent water bodies. In the case that there is no waterlogging (always run on well-defined banks) it will be scored following the criteria of a large waterhole.

⁵ Signs of wildlife (feces, rootings, footprints) were quantified by slowly walking in a 10 m-width band around each point.

⁶ In the case that there is waterlogging, it is considered a waterhole.

References

Martínez-Guijosa J, Lima-Barbero JF, Acevedo P, Cano-Terriza D, Jiménez-Ruiz S, Barasona JÁ, Boadella M, García-Bocanegra I, Gortázar C, Vicente J. Description and implementation of an On-farm Wildlife Risk Mitigation Protocol at the wildlife-livestock interface: Tuberculosis in Mediterranean environments. *Prev Vet Med.* 2021 Jun;191:105346. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105346.